

MODELLING THE EFFECTS OF COGNITIVE ABILITIES AND STUDY HABITS ON THE MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS AT TALAVERA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

Christine Joy F. Escobio, LPT, MAED ¹, Jhan Michael F. Bañez, LPT, MAED ²,
Pepito L. Naco, Ph.D. ³

¹ *Talavera National High School, Talavera, Nueva Ecija, Philippines*

² *EMA EMITS College Philippines, Pinamalayan, Oriental Mindoro, Philippines*

³ *Core Gateway College, Inc., San Jose City, Nueva Ecija, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the cognitive abilities, study habits, and mathematics performance of Grade 7 students at Talavera National High School. Specifically, the research assesses the extent of students' cognitive skills and study habits, as well as the level of mathematics performance of grade 7 students at Talavera National High School. Additionally, the study examines how cognitive abilities and study habits impact mathematics performance. The research employed a quantitative approach, collecting data from 140 Grade 7 students across various sections of Talavera National High School. Descriptive statistics were used to assess cognitive abilities, study habits, and mathematics performance. In contrast, inferential statistics were applied to determine the effects of cognitive skills and study habits on mathematics performance. Findings revealed that students exhibited high cognitive skills, particularly in attention, memory retention, logical reasoning, and audiovisual processing. Students also demonstrated strong study habits, especially in attending lectures, reading books, and practicing tests. Furthermore, most students achieved satisfactory to very satisfactory levels in mathematics. Although cognitive abilities did not significantly affect mathematics performance, the study found that certain study habits, particularly attending lectures, reading books, and practicing tests, had a significant positive impact. The study concludes that effective study habits are crucial in enhancing mathematics performance, while cognitive abilities, although necessary, do not directly influence mathematics

performance. This research highlights the importance of developing effective study habits in students to improve their academic performance, particularly in subjects such as mathematics.

Keywords: *Cognitive Abilities, Study Habits, Mathematical Performance, Attending Lectures, Reading Books*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical performance is a significant predictor of academic success and a necessary tool for survival in the 21st century. Despite this, improving management's performance in math remains a persistent challenge for global education systems. Researchers have identified several elements that significantly influence student performance, particularly in mathematics, over the past few decades. Several studies have found that learning mathematics is seriously predicted by the type of school.

International studies highlight significant gaps in mathematics performance, which are attributed to factors such as socioeconomic inequalities, insufficient resources, and variations in the quality of instruction. The interruption of learning induced by school closures and the shift to remote learning was at risk of dramatically affecting students' outcomes, particularly in the subject of mathematics, which requires ongoing practice and a deep understanding of information. In the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results for 2022, the Philippines ranked 6th out of 81 participating countries in mathematics, science, and reading. Filipino students had an average score of 355 points in mathematics, which is considerably lower than the global average of 487 points. While some encouraging improvements can be seen relative to the last time the test was administered in 2018, more than 70% of Filipino learners failed to meet the minimum proficiency levels expected for these content areas (OECD, 2022). This highlights the ongoing challenges in Philippine education, where advocates have called for reforms to improve student performance.

Even on a national stage, the challenges remain high, including declining test scores, a de-emphasis on conceptual understanding, and the need to create curricula that meet modern-day needs. The National Achievement Test (NAT) results for the Philippines in Grade 6 Mathematics were alarming. Mathematics Mean Percentage Score (MPS) was at a low of 34.76% in 2016-2017 and only improved to 36.86% in 2017-2018. These scores fell under the "low proficiency" category, marking a significant gap compared to previous years, such as the 2011-2012 school year, when the MPS was 66.47% (Philippine Basic Education, 2019; Behiga, 2022). These reflect the obstacles to attaining proficiency among students, especially across the K-12 program horizon. This persistent poor performance necessitates reforms in teaching strategies, curriculum, and resource allocation to enhance student performance in Mathematics.

In the context of individual schools, students often experience low motivation, weak foundational skills, and inadequate support, which collectively lead to poor performance

in mathematics. According to the pre-test result of the Project All-Numerates Assessment conducted at Talavera National High School on September 10, 2024, the mean score was 51.92. These scores fell under the "non-numerates" category. The results show a problem in the students' mathematics performance.

The abovementioned problem signifies that students' performance in Mathematics needs to be addressed. The researcher conceived the idea of investigating the impact of cognitive abilities and study habits on mathematics performance.

Cognitive abilities encompass memory retention, attention, logical reasoning, and processing speed, all impacting learning and academic performance (Liang et al., 2020). Mathematics requires analytical thinking and problem-solving, and heavily depends on these mental processes to develop meaningful comprehension and proficiency. In the words of Shi and Qu (2022), "Cognitive ability is crucial to both academic success and lifelong learning."

Moreover, study habits refer to students' behavior, attitudes, and practices in their academic tasks (Crede & Kuncel, 2008). Attending lectures, reading books, visiting the library, and practicing tests are essential for acquiring complicated subjects like mathematics (Prasetyo et al., 2019). Practice and instruction are essential for developing and refining study habits, which are not innate. According to Verma et al (2022), students' study habits impact their approach to learning, retention of knowledge, and preparation for evaluations. Developing effective study habits for educators and students can help bridge performance gaps and enhance learning outcomes (Rabia et al., 2017). In this manner, schools will identify the need to emphasize productive study strategies and traditional instruction.

Hence, recognizing the unique study habits associated with improved outcomes can enable the development of tailored education programs. Moreover, understanding the relationship between cognitive abilities and mathematical performance may be instrumental in designing tailored teaching approaches. Understanding the specific dimensions of mental skills and study habits may enlighten their influence on mathematically oriented tasks. In addition, knowing their relationship will help teachers to develop specific interventions that improve the mathematics outcome. Thus, this study aims to inform the differences in learning processes that can support the improvement of mathematical skills among students and the mechanisms of support that can facilitate this improvement.

Considering that this study focuses on the interaction between cognitive abilities, study habits, and mathematics performance, Grade 7 students were chosen as participants for several reasons. Their openness and responsiveness to new experiences and educational interventions make them highly responsive participants on whom researchers could investigate several dynamics, from motivation and engagement to collaborative and individual outcomes. Their diversity in terms of skill and capacity for learning at their level offers fertile data for analyzing and gathering salient information relevant to this study.

In line with this, the researchers aimed to investigate the effects of cognitive abilities and study habits on mathematics performance, as well as how specific mental skills and study habits influence students' mathematics performance.

Research Questions

This study generally aimed to determine the Cognitive Abilities, Study Habits, and Mathematics Performance of grade 7 students at Talavera National High School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the extent of cognitive abilities of grade 7 students at Talavera National High School in terms of:
 - 1.1. attention;
 - 1.2. auditory and visual processing;
 - 1.3. logical reasoning; and
 - 1.4. memory retention?
2. What is the extent of study habits of grade 7 students at Talavera National High School in terms of:
 - 2.1. attending lectures;
 - 2.2. reading books;
 - 2.3. visiting the library; and
 - 2.4. practicing tests?
3. What is the level of mathematics performance of grade 7 students at Talavera National High School?
4. What is the effect of cognitive abilities and study habits on the mathematics performance of grade 7 students at Talavera National High School?

METHODOLOGY

This quantitative study employed a descriptive-predictive research design, which involves collecting and analyzing numerical data to answer research questions (de Vaus, 2001). The study's descriptive statistics focused on the extent of specific dimensions of cognitive abilities, study habits, and mathematics performance. Meanwhile, the predictive aspect examined the effects of these dimensions.

The study used multiple regression analysis as the primary statistical tool within the quantitative design framework. The sample size assumed a power of 80%, a 5% significance level, and a medium effect size of 0.15. Considering the number of independent variables, the study requires at least 114 responses. The research added 20% extra samples to address potential responses, incomplete data, and sample losses. A survey of approximately 140 participants was conducted to secure robust data while meeting or exceeding the needed minimum sample size for analysis. This design method provided the proper statistical power to detect medium effects while preserving the reliability of multiple regression analysis outcomes. The adjustment method reduced

study uncertainties associated with missing data, strengthening the research findings' robustness.

Stratified random sampling, a method that divides a population into distinct subgroups, or "strata," was used to determine the number of respondents in the study. In this study, the target population was stratified according to the section to which the student belongs, and then participants were randomly selected from each stratum.

A self-made questionnaire and students' grades are the two primary components that were utilized in this study. The questionnaire was designed to collect quantitative data from participants regarding their perceptions, experiences, and attitudes regarding student cognitive abilities and study habits. The questionnaire focused on measuring the specific dimension of Cognitive Abilities such as attention, retention, logical reasoning, and audio and visual processing, which is adapted from the four (4) different types of Cognitive Abilities written by Indeed Editorial Team (2024), and Study Habits in terms of attending lectures, reading books, visiting the library, and practicing test which is adapted from the study of Prasetyo et al (2019).

Meanwhile, grades in official school records were used as a secondary data set to analyze mathematics achievement objectively. The mean of the first and second quarters was calculated to assess the student's performance in mathematics.

In addition, the reliability test method was employed to ensure that the extent of cognitive abilities and study habits was reliable. Thirty students who were not included in the study but were at the same grade level were asked to complete the questionnaire twice within a ten-day interval.

Furthermore, construct validity was used to examine the accuracy of the intended construct: cognitive abilities and study habits. The questionnaire was validated by mathematics experts, who are teachers with a master's degree in the field. Then, the questionnaire was revised based on the corrections and suggestions provided by the validators. Hence, it is comprehensive enough to cover the variables intended in the study, and the items adequately represent the subject to be addressed as evaluated.

The collected data were treated carefully, classified, and statistically organized according to the criteria established in the instrument. The study employed descriptive statistics, including frequency distributions; summary statistics, such as mean and standard deviation; and inferential statistics, including multiple regression.

The scope of this study focuses on modeling the effects of cognitive abilities- specifically attention, memory retention, logical reasoning, and auditory and visual processing- and study habits, including attending lectures, reading books, visiting the library, and practicing tests, on mathematics performance of grade 7 students at Talavera National high School. Mathematics performance was the dependent variable of the study which is directly obtained from the mean grades of the students from the first two quarters of school year 2024-2025.

Meanwhile, this study was limited to learners enrolled in Grade 7 at Talavera National High School of school year 2024-2025 and concentrates solely on their performance in mathematics as measured by the mean of their most recent academic records. The study does not include other schools, grade levels, subjects, and other external factors that may also affect mathematics performance. Additionally, data collected rely on self-made questionnaires that were adopted from Indeed Editorial Team (2024) and the study of Prasetyo et al (2019) and student's grades, which may introduce response bias or incomplete information. Despite these limitations, the study aims to provide a more robust result that focus on understanding how selected cognitive abilities and study habits contribute to the mathematics performance of Grade 7 learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Extent of Cognitive Abilities

Cognitive Skills in terms of:	Overall Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Attention	2.75	0.81	High Extent
Memory Retention	2.76	0.80	High Extent
Logical Reasoning	2.82	0.81	High Extent
Auditory and Visual Processing	3.15	0.79	High Extent

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	Very High Extent
2.51 – 3.25	High Extent
1.76 – 2.50	Low Extent
1.00 – 1.75	Very Low Extent

Table 1 shows that the respondents are highly attentive in class, as indicated in the overall mean of 2.75. Moreover, the overall standard deviation of 0.81, shows that most of the responses are clustered around the mean, although values indicate some variability in response. The result shows that students are not easily distracted but maintain their focus on mathematical problems. As a result, they can quickly identify and recognize patterns in solving math problems. In addition, the result emphasizes that students possess a keen awareness of small details, which is crucial in solving mathematical problems. Similarly, Orbach and Fritz (2022) state that sustained attention enables students to focus on detailed problems and to work step by step toward the solution.

Aside from being attentive in class, generally the respondents exhibit a strong memory retention ability among various task as reflected from the overall mean of 2.76. Correspondingly, the overall standard deviation of 0.80, suggests that while students generally agree on their memory retention abilities, there is still some variation in their responses. The result shows that students emphasize the ability to recall formulas, rules, and procedures, retain and apply past concepts to new topics, and remember problem-solving strategies demonstrated by teachers. Additionally, students with strong memory retention showcase the capacity to store and retrieve multiple steps in complex processes

and recognize connections between mathematical topics for solving integrated problems. This is parallel to the claims of Comighud et al (2020) that retaining mathematical information helps learners build on previously-held knowledge, which leads to a heightened understanding of the subject matter.

In addition, the respondents possess strong logical reasoning skills in mathematics, including the ability to analyze problems step by step, recognize patterns, choose efficient problem-solving methods, and justify answers with reasoning with an overall mean score of 2.82. However, the overall standard deviation of 0.81, suggests a more significant variation in responses, showing that some students may feel confident in their logical reasoning skills while others are less proficient. The result implies that students with high logical reasoning tend to break down problems into small manageable parts, making it easier to find practical solutions. In line with the findings of Ramganes and Reddy (2021) which shows that student with stronger logical reasoning skills obtain higher academic success levels, especially in mathematics. Reasoning is an essential skill that leads to better problem-solving, decision-making, and overall cognitive efficiency.

Furthermore, the result also shows that students also prefer auditory and visual learning in mathematics, as yielded in the overall mean of 3.15. Meanwhile, the overall standard deviation suggests that students have a generally consistent perception of their auditory and visual processing abilities, with some variation. While many students rate their cognitive abilities similarly, some perceive them as higher or lower, leading to moderate response dispersion. The result emphasizes students' ability to understand concepts better through diagrams, visual aids, and step-by-step demonstrations and to retain information more effectively from videos, animations, and spoken instructions. Students with this preference find it easier to remember things when they hear and see the teacher's discussions and presentations. Videos and other multimedia tools allow learners to link theoretical knowledge to real-life examples, enhancing the interactivity and engagement of the learning experience (Patahuddin et al., 2022). Similarly, students who rely more on auditory processing tend to perform well on verbal explanations and discussions (Bearneza, 2023).

Table 2. Extent of Study Habits

Study Habits in terms of:	Overall Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Attending Lectures	3.14	0.79	High Extent
Reading Books	2.73	0.84	High Extent
Visiting the Library	2.53	0.90	High Extent
Practicing Test	3.07	0.79	High Extent

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	Very High Extent
2.51 – 3.25	High Extent
1.76 – 2.50	Low Extent
1.00 – 1.75	Very Low Extent

Table 2 shows that students regularly attend lectures as reflected on the overall mean of 3.14. However, the overall standard deviation of 0.79 suggests that while students generally agree on the extent to which they attend lectures, there is still some variation in their responses. This means that while many students regularly attend lectures, some do so to a lesser or greater extent. The result implies that students enhance their learning by attending lectures on time, actively listening, taking notes, and asking questions. They also discuss and review materials before and after class to reinforce understanding. Regular attendance allows students to grasp the concepts directly from instructors, leading to better understanding and retention of knowledge. Similarly, Lindsay and Evans (2022) revealed that hands-on involvement in traditional lectures enhances the understanding of authoritative mathematical concepts more than other active learning strategies. Also, the longer hours a student is attending lectures, the greater his or her performance will be, similar to other studies that indicated that higher exposure to structured learning increases the student's knowledge of the subject matter studied (Gogo et al., 2022).

Likewise, with an overall mean of 2.73, generally students read books extensively. Just as the overall standard deviation of 0.84 suggests that students' responses are stable and clustered around the mean. This shows that while most students engage in reading books to a great extent, their responses still show some variability, though not extreme. The result shows that students seek additional references to enhance their understanding of mathematics concepts. Regular reading and note-taking help reinforce concepts, while structured study methods ensure logical progression in learning. Seeking additional resources and revisiting books help students grasp important details and deepen their understanding of the subject. Parallel to the claims of Belano (2024), "a student's grasp of oral reading enables them to process and communicate mathematical ideas, which improves their problem-solving abilities". Furthermore, reading skills, as shown in the Žakelj et al (2019) study, play a fundamental role in interpreting mathematical texts and in making sense of word problems through applying mathematical reasoning.

Similarly, with a computed overall mean of 2.53, students frequently visit the library to seek additional information needed to deepen their mathematical content knowledge. Moreover, the overall standard deviation of 0.90 suggest a moderate variability in how frequently students visit the library. Some students may visit often, while others rarely do, leading to a broader spread of responses. The result shows that students prefer to use the library to review and clarify complex mathematical concepts for their study because of its quiet environment. Regular access to library resources provides students with the tools and support needed for success in mathematics, thus showing the critical link to academic success (Fagyan et al., 2023).

Correspondingly, data revealed that students actively practice tests, as indicated in the overall mean of 3.07. However, the overall standard deviation score of 0.79 suggests a relatively stable pattern in students' responses, meaning test practice is a common and consistent habit among them. The result shows that students regularly practice test-taking before the exam to familiarize themselves with and understand mathematical concepts. This helps improve retention and recall by reinforcing learned

concepts, making it easier to remember key information during actual exams. Regular test practice enhances time management skills, helping students allocate their time effectively and complete exams within the given timeframe. In line with the study of Alenton (2022) that students being exposed to the material multiple times (called "testing") improves retention and increases student confidence while enhancing performance in hard or complex problems. Such mathematics tests reinforce mathematics concepts, promote active learning, and develop a culture of self-improvement (Avvisati & Borgonovi, 2020).

Table 3. Level of Mathematics Performance

GRADE RANGE	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
70-74 (Did Not Meet Expectations)	0	0
75-79 (Fairly Satisfactory)	10	7.19
80-84 (Satisfactory)	48	34.53
85-89 (Very Satisfactory)	58	41.73
90-94 (Outstanding)	23	16.55
Mean (SD)	85.56 (4)	
Min, Max	77, 90	

SD: Standard Deviation; Min = Minimum; Max =Maximum

*The grading scale was based on DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015.

Data reveals that no students (0%) got a grade of 70 to 74, meaning everyone met at least the "Fairly Satisfactory" level. In addition, 10 students (7.19%) got a grade of 75 to 79, indicating a small portion of students had just above the passing mark. Moreover, 48 students (34.53%) fell to the satisfactory level, showing that a significant portion performed moderately. Furthermore, 58 students (41.73%) got a grade that lies within a very satisfactory level, making it the most common performance level. At last, 23 students (16.55%) achieved high marks under the outstanding level, showing strong academic performance.

Most students (76.26%) scored satisfactory to very satisfactory (80-89 range), indicating strong overall performance. The lowest recorded grade is 77, while the highest is 90, meaning all students scored at least "Fairly Satisfactory," and none reached above 94. Since the lowest score is 77, it suggests that all students met at least the basic academic expectations, with no failing grades. The standard deviation from 81.56 to 89.56 indicates that most students' scores are within ± 4 points of the mean. The result suggests that most grades are clustered around the mean without extreme variations.

Table 4. Effects of Cognitive Abilities and Study Habits on Mathematics Performance

PREDICTOR	b	SE_b	p-value
(Intercept)	71.01	1.82	<0.001
Cognitive Abilities			
Attention	-0.13	0.84	0.876
Memory Retention	1.03	0.88	0.24
Logical Reasoning	1.36	0.95	0.156
Auditory and Visual Processing	0.36	0.85	0.672
Study Habits			
Attending Lectures	1.79	0.82	0.032*
Reading Books	1.72	0.72	0.018*
Visiting the Library	-0.89	0.56	0.118
Practicing Test	2.75	0.78	0.001**

Model Fit and Significance: $F(8,131)=14.17$, $p<.001$

R-squared: 46.4%

* indicates $p < .05$. ** indicates $p < .01$.

Note. b represents unstandardized regression weights; SE_b represents the standard error of the regression weights

p-value represents the probability value for statistical significance.

The table shows the overall regression model of the effect of cognitive abilities and study habits on mathematics performance. The table reveals that at least one of the predictors has a meaningful impact on mathematics performance, as reflected by the computed F-statistics ($F(8,131)=14.17$, $p<.001$), which is statistically significant.

To address it, data revealed that cognitive abilities in all indicators: attention ($b=-0.13$, $p=0.876$), memory retention ($b=1.03$, $p=0.24$), logical reasoning ($b=1.36$, $p=0.156$), and auditory and visual processing ($b=0.36$, $p=0.672$) have no significant effect on mathematics performance. The results show that although cognitive abilities are important, several factors can sometimes overshadow their impact. Some factors that directly affect mathematics performance are mathematical anxiety (Semeraro et al., 2020), self-efficacy and motivation, study strategies, and teacher support and involvement (Cabalquinto & Magallanes, 2022). High levels of math anxiety can hinder performance, regardless of a student's cognitive abilities (Semeraro et al., 2020). Students with high self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation are more likely to engage deeply with mathematical content, leading to better performance. Effective study strategies, such as regular practice and active engagement with material, have been linked to improved mathematics outcomes. Supportive teachers and positive classroom environments can enhance students' attitudes toward mathematics, thereby boosting performance (Cabalquinto & Magallanes, 2022).

On the other hand, attending lectures ($b=1.79$, $p=0.032$) and reading books ($b=1.72$, $p=0.018$) shows significance at $p<0.05$, indicating that students who regularly attend lectures and read books tend to perform better in Math. Moreover, practicing tests ($b=2.75$, $p=0.001$) shows significance at $p<0.01$, indicating that students who frequently

practice tests tend to achieve better math performance. Similarly, Balbacal (2023) emphasizes that well-established study habits, such as regular practice, time management, note-taking, and active engagement with mathematical problems, are closely linked to higher mathematics achievement levels. In addition, Getape and Quitorio (2023) found a strong link between effective study habits and academic success.

However, visiting the library ($b=-0.89$, $p=0.118$) is insignificant, indicating that visiting the library does not predict mathematics performance. The results show that while libraries provide a valuable resource for learning, their impact on math performance depends on how students utilize them. Passive engagement with math materials does not yield the same benefits as active learning techniques like practicing problems, attending lectures, and taking practice tests. Similarly, Scoulas and De Groote (2019) found that the frequency of library use does not always correlate with the student's academic grades; more importantly, students perceive their library use as having a positive impact on their grades. Their finding highlights that merely visiting the library does not guarantee improved academic performance; instead, how students utilize library resources plays a more significant role.

Furthermore, the R-squared value suggests that cognitive abilities and study habits can explain 46.4% of the variance in math performance.

Conclusions

The findings reveal that Grade 7 students at Talavera National High School exhibit high cognitive abilities. The most substantial cognitive strength was observed in audio and visual processing, showing that students learn best through visual and auditory methods. Logical reasoning also ranked high, reflecting students' ability to analyze and solve complex problems effectively. However, while still at a high level, attention and memory retention showed slightly lower mean scores and some variation, indicating that certain students may need additional support in maintaining focus and recalling information effectively.

At the same time, grade 7 students also exhibit a high extent of study habits. The students prioritize attending lectures and test practice as key study habits, contributing to their understanding of mathematical concepts. Their engagement in reading books also plays a significant role in reinforcing knowledge, though with some variation. However, visiting the library is the least study habit, indicating that students may prefer other sources of information, such as online resources or class materials.

Moreover, the results indicate that Grade 7 students generally perform well in mathematics, with most achieving satisfactory or higher grades. The absence of failing scores suggests that all students have at least a foundational understanding of the subject. The small number of students in the Fairly Satisfactory level may require additional support to improve their performance. However, the majority scoring in the Satisfactory to Outstanding level highlights strong academic competence in mathematics.

Additionally, the study reveals that practicing tests is the highest predictor of significant performance among the various study habits. However, although cognitive abilities are important, they do not significantly affect mathematics performance. Some factors, like affective and non-cognitive factors, overshadow this effect.

In conclusion, the findings indicate that study habits are more crucial in students' academic success, particularly in mathematics. Specifically, attending lectures, reading books, and practicing tests are significant predictors of mathematics performance, with test practice showing the most substantial effect.

Recommendations

Based on the drawn conclusion, teachers should integrate higher-order thinking activities, including logical reasoning tasks, pattern recognition, and analytical problem-solving, to strengthen students' cognitive processing.

Schools and educators must promote structured, consistent study routines that encourage time management and self-discipline. Students should be guided to develop effective note-taking strategies, actively participate in lectures, incorporate practice tests, and use self-assessment methods. This will allow students to evaluate their understanding and identify areas for improvement.

Teachers should adopt engaging and interactive teaching methods, including hands-on activities, real-life applications, and technology-based learning tools, to make mathematical concepts more accessible and relatable. Encouraging regular assessment and feedback also shapes students' growth, motivation, and long-term success.

Students should prioritize effective study habits, particularly attending lectures, reading books, and practicing tests regularly. Educational institutions should encourage these habits by providing structured study programs, accessible learning materials, and opportunities for students to engage in self-assessment.

Since the R-squared got low, future researchers can use other variables, such as affective factors and other non-cognitive abilities, to test whether they significantly affect mathematics performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Participants were informed about the study, its purpose, data collection procedures, and confidentiality measures explained. Their identities were kept anonymous, and the data was stored securely. Any information collected was used solely for this study. Participation was voluntary, and participants could withdraw at any time without penalty. The participants avoided physical and psychological harm.

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